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NEDIE B. SEVILLA, PhD

Associate Professor II

Dr. Emilio B. Espinosa Sr. Memorial State College of
Agriculture and Technology

nedie.sevilla@debesmcat.edu.ph

“THE CRUMBS”

Looking down, my finger brushes across your eyelashes,
Grouped in little points from your fight with sleep.
I gently wipe the crumbs from your parted lips and
Kiss the streaks on your cheeks.
I smooth your stringy hair
From your forehead and place your finger in your curled
Such a beautiful little person, your face so innocent, though for so long I do not know.
Perhaps I should have left the crumbs.